

Wind power development and biodiversity¹

By Hiroyuki Matsuda

Developing renewable energy is a key policy for mitigating climate change. Both Japan's climate change documents and the "National Biodiversity Strategy 2023-2030" state that "carbon neutrality" and "a society in harmony with nature" must be achieved by 2050.¹ However, introducing renewable energy requires adjustments to avoid adverse effects. Additionally, it is stated that trade-offs with the introduction of renewable energy must be avoided. Bird strikes are a particular concern regarding wind power generation.

01 Trade-offs Between Climate Change Impacts and Mitigation Measures

In risk theory, a trade-off is a constraint in which one objective variable is a monotonically decreasing function of another. In the case of renewable energy, contributing to mitigation measures promotes biodiversity worldwide. However, this process involves changes in land use and has an impact on the local environment, albeit less than hydropower dams and thermal power plants do. When it comes to trade-offs, we usually look for a solution that is desirable overall rather than choosing between two options. However, it is unclear whether the above "avoidance" refers to such a compromise. It could also mean approving renewable energy as long as it does not affect biodiversity.

Climate change is one of the five primary threats to biodiversity, alongside habitat loss, overexploitation, pollution, and invasive species. Mitigating climate change helps protect life globally. In this context, however, a trade-off often arises between global and local biodiversity. While the construction of wind power plants contributes to global biodiversity conservation by reducing greenhouse gas emissions, it can negatively impact local biodiversity. Renewable energy can be considered beneficial overall when the positive impact on global biodiversity outweighs the local biodiversity loss. However, such evaluations are rarely, if ever, reflected in environmental impact assessments (EIAs) for renewable energy projects in Japan.

Since each business's contribution to mitigation measures is included in an EIA evaluation, we can evaluate each business's contribution to global biodiversity if we can evaluate the impact of greenhouse gas reductions on global biodiversity. The following is not a peer-reviewed estimate, so the figures may change. Let me explain my thinking.

¹ This is my personal translation of an article originally published on the Think Nature website.

<https://np-journal.jp/articles/academia-09/>

Figure 1. Predicted impacts on biodiversity .Ohashi et al. (2019)ⁱⁱ

In fact, climate change mitigation measures do not always contribute to the conservation of global biodiversity. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has developed scenarios that project the effects of climate change and land use changes resulting from these efforts. These countermeasures often entail substantial changes in land use, including expanding biofuel crop cultivation. Since land use changes are one of the greatest threats to biodiversity, alongside climate change—the IPCC’s primary focus—researchers use tools such as species distribution models to predict the potential future habitats of various taxa.

For example, Ohashi et al. (2019) show that limiting the global temperature increase to 2°C through mitigation measures provides more protection for species habitats than allowing a 4°C rise without such measures (Figure 1). However, the land changes required for mitigation could pose a greater threat to biodiversity. Another studyⁱⁱⁱ predicts that the difference in the impact on biodiversity between a 3°C and a 2°C increase may be minimal because the benefits of limiting warming could be offset by the negative effects of land use changes.

Furthermore, the IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report^{iv} estimates that 3%-14% of species in terrestrial ecosystems face an extremely high risk of extinction with a 1.5°C temperature increase; 3%-18% with a 2°C increase; 3%-29% with a 3°C increase; and 3%-48% with a 5°C increase. While the upper bound of the risk increases with warming, the lower bound remains consistently around 3%. This likely reflects the baseline level of habitat loss caused by land use changes associated with mitigation efforts.

It is also important to note that climate change mitigation helps protect marine biodiversity. Although marine biodiversity is not directly impacted by land use changes, it is highly vulnerable to rising temperatures and ocean acidification.

The contribution of wind power plants to climate change mitigation can be assessed by the amount of CO₂ emissions they offset. For example, replacing liquefied natural gas (LNG)-fired power generation with wind power would result in a 100 MW

wind farm operating at a 20% capacity factor (the threshold for commercial viability) would generate approximately 3.5 TWh of electricity over 20 years. Since LNG-fired power generation emits approximately 474 grams of CO₂ per kWh (not including indirect emissions from facility construction and other sources), the wind farm would reduce CO₂ emissions by about 1.6 million tons over 20 years.

However, constructing renewable energy facilities also results in CO₂ emissions. For example, clearing forested land affects local ecosystems and releases stored carbon. Forests store around 800 tons of CO₂ per hectare and can absorb approximately 230 tons over 20 years. Therefore, if 1 km² (100 hectares) of forest is cleared, the resulting indirect emissions would total approximately 100,000 tons of CO₂.

In most cases, the reduction in CO₂ achieved through renewable energy generation far outweighs the greenhouse gas emissions associated with construction. Furthermore, if a wind power plant were rebuilt on the same site after 20 years, no additional deforestation would be required, and much of the forest would likely have regenerated by then. However, it is not guaranteed that the original tree species will return. This means that the long-term impact on biodiversity depends on which species reestablish themselves.

Sugiyama Taishi has published a similar calculation online for solar panels^v. In his analysis, he assumes that the introduction of new solar power plants displaces not only thermal power but also hydroelectric, nuclear, and other renewable energy sources on average. As a result, the estimated mitigation effect is smaller than in the previous wind power example.

IPCC reports document the relationship between temperature rise and greenhouse gas emissions. According to these estimates, reducing CO₂ emissions by one ton leads to a decrease in global warming of approximately 0.5×10^{-12} °C. Therefore, reducing CO₂ emissions by 1.5 million tons would correspond to an estimated decrease in the rate of global temperature rise of about 0.7×10^{-6} °C.

The predicted difference in the percentage of species at high risk of extinction between 1.5°C and 3°C of global warming is estimated to be 0%–9%. However, this estimate reflects both the positive effect of preserving habitats by limiting global warming and the negative effect of habitat loss due to mitigation measures. The negative impact should be assessed in relation to the renewable energy facility itself. In other words, the global benefit of climate change mitigation must be weighed against the local ecological cost of constructing each renewable energy facility. The latter is typically evaluated through Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) conducted for individual projects.

Compared to biofuel plantations or large-scale dam developments, such as those on the Amazon River, the ecological impact of wind power facilities is likely orders of magnitude smaller.

Taking the above into account, it should be possible to estimate the effect of preserving global species habitats per ton of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduced. While the detailed calculations should be addressed in future academic studies, a framework could be developed to estimate the net contribution to biodiversity by weighing the positive effects of GHG mitigation against the negative impacts of facility construction. Moreover, climate change mitigation measures offer a broad range of co-benefits—not only for biodiversity but also for public health, industrial productivity, and other aspects of human well-being.

02 Bird Collision Risk and Cumulative Impacts

The Ministry of the Environment in Japan conducts risk assessments related to environmental chemicals, endangered species, and bird collisions caused by wind power facilities. For bird collisions, a methodology has been developed to estimate collision risk prior to turbine construction.^{vi}

As part of the environmental impact assessment (EIA) process, pre-construction surveys are conducted to track bird flight trajectories. These data are then used to estimate how frequently birds will pass through the rotor-swept zone of the turbines, with a particular focus on rare or protected species such as sea eagles. After construction, bird behavior is further considered by incorporating the "avoidance rate"—the likelihood that birds will detect and avoid the turbines. While this rate cannot be directly measured before construction, it is often inferred from studies conducted in other regions.

For instance, in Japan's first bird collision risk assessment case—at the Awara Kitagata Wind Power Plant in Fukui Prefecture—an avoidance rate of over 99% was assumed, based on a Danish study of geese. According to the business operator's EIA, of the approximately 3,000 white-fronted geese that overwinter at Katano Kamoike Pond, a Ramsar-listed wetland, only about one collision per year was predicted based on flight frequency over the proposed site^{vii}. However, the Wild Bird Society of Japan published different flight frequency data, predicting approximately 20 collisions per year.

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This example shows how risk assessment outcomes can differ greatly depending on the data used. The accuracy of these predictions will only become clear once the wind turbines are in operation.

If bird collisions occur significantly more frequently than predicted, risk can be reduced through operational restrictions^{viii}. While this may affect business profitability, it is often possible to estimate the extent of management intervention that can be implemented while maintaining financial profit. Such assessments depend on several factors, including the construction and maintenance costs of the wind power facility, the electricity selling price, and the capacity factor.

In the case of the Awara Kitagata Wind Power Plant, it was agreed that human monitors would be stationed for the first two years of operation. Additionally, a system was implemented to stop the turbines within a few seconds if a flock of wild geese was detected approaching. These kinds of measures represent a form of adaptive management—an approach where ongoing monitoring is conducted after project implementation and mitigation measures are modified based on actual conditions.

There is currently no fixed standard for what constitutes an acceptable level of bird collision risk. Rather than setting a zero-tolerance threshold for any single collision, ecological risk should be evaluated in terms of its potential impact on the overall population of the species concerned.

One commonly used indicator is the PBR (Potential Biological Removal). Originally developed in the United States to determine acceptable bycatch levels of rare

marine mammals, the concept has also been applied to the Awara Kitagata project. PBR is calculated using a conservative population estimate (N), the maximum natural annual population growth rate (R), and a recovery factor (Fr), which adjusts for the species' conservation status. The formula is:

$$PBR = NRF_r/2.$$

The recovery factor (Fr) is typically set at 1 for least concerned species, 0.5 for vulnerable species, and 0.1 for endangered species.

For example, in the case of the white-fronted geese at Katano Kamoike, assuming $N=3000$, $R=0.12$, and $Fr=0.5$, the resulting PBR would be $3,000 \times 0.12 \times 0.5 / 2 = 90$ birds per year. This value represents the upper limit of allowable human-induced mortality across all causes—not just collisions with wind turbines. In practice, human-induced bird mortality is far more commonly associated with collisions with buildings, predation by domestic cats, power line electrocutions, vehicle strikes, and train accidents^{ix}. However, in the specific case of the geese at Katano Kamoike, the number of such deaths from other causes is likely to be relatively low.

In the case of the Awara Kitagata Wind Power Plant, the actual bird collision risk—which turned out to be minimal—was the main concern. If collision incidents had significantly exceeded the predictions made in the environmental impact assessment (EIA), the operator would have been required to implement additional mitigation measures, even if the total number of human-caused fatalities, including collisions, remained below the PBR threshold. Fortunately, since the plant began commercial operations in 2011, not a single collision has been reported.

In contrast, several wind power facilities in Hokkaido have experienced fatal collisions involving white-tailed eagles, raising concerns about cumulative impacts. In such cases, PBR may be a useful evaluation standard.

There are two distinct populations of white-tailed eagles: migratory individuals that breed in Russia and resident birds that breed in Japan^x. The Ministry of the Environment does not differentiate between the two populations in its assessments. However, the migratory population is relatively large, and the species is listed as Least Concern (LC) on the IUCN Red List^{xi}. The resident population in Japan, however, is estimated at only 700–1,000 individuals with a natural annual increase rate of 16–21%^{xii}. This population is classified as Endangered Species II on the Ministry's Red List. Using the PBR formula with conservative estimates and assuming $N = 1,000$, $R = 0.16$, and $Fr = 0.5$, PBR is about 40 birds: $1,000 \times 0.16 \times 0.5 / 2$.

From 2018 to 2023, an average of 30.4 birds were captured due to human-caused deaths other than wind-related causes per year, of which 4.6 were killed by wind turbines^{xiii}. This number likely includes migratory birds. Additionally, there may be uncaptured or undiscovered human-caused deaths. The current monitoring system does not distinguish between migratory and resident birds, so it is difficult to assess the cumulative impact based on the PBR. However, some resident individuals can be identified based on individual cases and timing.

Most collision deaths, especially in the winter, are discovered by operators during maintenance patrols. In the case of monthly patrols, the probability that carcasses are not carried away by carnivores is about 50%^{xiv}, and the number of carcasses discovered is probably about half of the total number of collision deaths. Assuming an appropriate detection rate makes it possible to set an upper limit on the number of human-caused deaths.

However, it is difficult to determine how operators should respond if the upper limit is exceeded. Rather than waiting for new entrants, operators receiving more electricity than they generate should take action. Alternatively, it may be a good idea to create a system in which operators can take cost-effective measures and the costs are shared by all operators.

From 2023 to 2025, there were 10 collisions involving white-tailed sea eagles and one collision involving Steller's sea eagles reported at Hamasato Wind Farm in Horonobe Town, Hokkaido, less than two years after the farm began operating. The operators took the situation seriously, installing sonic deterrent devices. However, collisions continued, prompting the suspension of daytime operations for all 14 units^{xv}. . Since the deterrent devices record collision scenes, further investigation into the cause of the collisions is needed.

Regarding migratory birds, it has been suggested that, in addition to dying from collisions, they may be affected by wind turbines and that avoiding them may increase their flight distances. Birds may forget about the turbines immediately after spotting food and crash into them. However, eliminating feeding grounds near wind turbines reduces their carrying capacity. Whether it is necessary to avoid them to the point of increasing flight distances is controversial.

Offshore wind power generation may have negative ecological impacts, but it can also have positive effects. For example, it can function as an artificial reef. According to the informal opinion of Japan Society for Ocean Policy volunteers, "if scientific monitoring and evaluation following the installation of wind power facilities reveals a positive impact on marine biodiversity, these areas may qualify as OECMs (Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures, Matsuda's note)"^{xvi}.

In 2023, the national and local governments began selecting suitable sites for offshore wind power generation and inviting operators through a competitive bidding process known as the "Centralized System."^{xvii} However, under Japan's EIA system, the effects on fisheries are considered separately from environmental impacts, and whether consensus building will proceed smoothly remains an open question. Renewable energy projects typically involve high initial equipment costs and low operation and maintenance costs. Moreover, since wind turbines are often manufactured overseas, it is difficult to ensure that profits are returned to the local community. The National Biodiversity Strategy recommends "advancing climate change measures in a way that coexists with the local community." If local residents and fishers are involved in project management, for example, it may be possible to distribute profits more equitably.

Ideally, wind turbines would be located in areas with favorable wind conditions that have minimal impact on birds and ecosystems^{xviii}. However, in practice, site selection is often constrained by land ownership and regulatory factors. For instance, the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries in Japan reportedly restricts the construction of turbines on agricultural land.

Although wind and other renewable energy sources are expected to play a crucial role in mitigating climate change, the deployment of these types of facilities in Japan has not gone smoothly. Consequently, achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement is uncertain.

ⁱ「生物多様性国家戦略 2023-2030」<https://www.biodic.go.jp/biodiversity/about/initiatives/index.html>

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